

TRAINING OF STUDENTS TO TOLERANT RELATIONS IN THE PROCESS OF HIGHER EDUCATION.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8227346>

One of the most important requirements of today's is the support on humanistic ideas in mutual relations of teacher and teacher in modern education system. One of these requirements consists in that, as pupils, and teachers concern tolerantly interpersonal relations in the process of training. Reception of such skill also is important for achievement of qualitative changes in formation. To understand this problem, it is desirable to underline the tolerance concept.

For the first time Russian psychologist B.G.Ananyev applied tolerance in the sixties of the last century while the social psychology of this phenomenon was studied by Petersburg scientist G.L.Bardier.

Concept of tolerance were been described by experts in various areas. In particular, tolerance occurs from Latin word "tolerantia" and is used in philosophy for expression of tolerance, impartiality and philosophy, and in psychological terms - endurance, persistence, tolerance and broadmindedness.

In purely psychological sense tolerance is the union which defines ability of the person to co-operate with an external world in problem and critical situations, to restore own nervous and psychological balance, to achieve success in adaptation, to avoid animosities and to develop positive relations with world around, found out its maintenance.

As experts summarize, tolerance phenomenon can be differentiated as follows:

Tolerance of type A is an unconditional understanding of other person, its natural acceptance, relation to it as to the precious and most expensive nature of the nature. Such tolerance plays an important role in life of young men as personification process yet is not reached individual and social experience. If to speak simply, tolerance of+ type A, is possible to compare to innocence of children where they have direct understanding and feeling of others (for example, an adult cries, laughs and tries to calm him).

Tolerance of type A is a basis that small children were always kind to the parents. Some parents are severe with children - they bear psychological or physical punishment, but children accept parents as kind ones. Presence of

tolerance of type A will help to keep positive relation to psychological, subjective protection of person and negative prospects of cruel treatment.

Tolerance of type B is a voluntary part of person which is characteristic for self-expression. It is important to notice, that it often takes place for adults. Tolerant person even more often works, using protective mechanisms. Hence, it sometimes hides emotions, feelings or dissatisfaction and aggression. Hence, tolerance of type B can be interpreted as inexact, partially expressive, conditional or cultural tolerance. That is, if we look at this type of tolerance, it is possible to see following expressions: «we are patient with you, because...»; «situation is that, that we should suffer it, because...»; «at present I cannot be myself, and I should prove the patient»; «i think about something but I cannot tell it, because...». In these situations of the reason which follow after "reason", reflect necessity of influence of person on external influences. It is harmful to internal stresses of person and, as consequence, for health of person. Tolerance of type «B» naturally is accepted by person, and not just associates. Unlike tolerance of type A, this type of consciousness is directed on natural understanding of surrounding influences. Such tolerance, against violence and manipulations, reflects internal values, which are valuable for other person, respect for value, emotions and acceptance them.

Reciprocity in relations between teacher and pupils comes not automatically, but because of tolerance of adults, that is their tolerance. Psychological research shows, that the psychological trauma and constant self-expression of teacher in mutual relations of pupil during his / her educational activity lead to development of authoritative intolerance.

Inter tolerant relations between teacher and pupil can lead to conflict finally. As the factor of occurrence of the conflict it is possible to count up conflicts in system of values. As, teacher - is a system of values which is specific to its age and an occupation. Students with higher probability will adhere to system of values which is inherent in their age and status.

In particular, difference in system of sights at estimations of pupils and teachers can make negative impact on tolerance. That is, if the pupil wishes to be always at high level of knowledge of pupil, so teachers will try to estimate its knowledge realistically. Dissatisfaction of self-confident students in the process of assessment also can be reason.

It also is connected with characteristic problems of pupils, in particular with their tolerance in relations with teacher - their intolerance.

If pupils are regularly analyzed nowadays, losing control in misunderstanding between teacher and them and getting ride out of it, can be considered in lower degree. It can be connected with absence of psychological knowledge, skills and experience on the other hand if they can be used as a result of various external influences and can be connected with inconveniences. Understandings of problem situations arising in the course of educational activity, and understanding of that they are «inaccessible», also make negative impact not only on a psychological condition of the pupil, but also on teaching and, the most important thing, on physiological health of the pupil. Considering importance of education of healthy and harmonious generation today, this problem is underlined again. Taking it into consideration, it would be expedient to raise psychological awareness of students.

Therefore it is necessary to generate tolerant relation to pupils' mind about the correct relation to the social and personal problems arising in the process of training. It even one of the best factors of increasing of stability.

To develop such skills and abilities, pupils are recommended to develop individual tolerance to problem situations.

Solution of problem situations, for example it means that tolerance demands, that student tries to find decision of these situations and tried to cope with difficulties connected by his or her life. Student uses these psychological factors, such as patience, persistence, rationality, trying not to lose sight of problem and not to pay to it attention. But such skills in human mind are not shown in pupils. In order to form them, students need such skills, as training, supervision, and going always forward in order to realize them.

According to many researchers, empathy plays an important role in tolerance formation. Considering it, today's education system has crucial importance for development of empathetic skills at teachers and students. Significance of these skills consists that it allows companion to co-operate with each other in the course of dialogue and to restore interdependent relations. The empathy also helps you to be patient to various emotions, it is better to understand emotions of people, to irritate them and to accept them without the worst.

There are some approaches of tolerance, one of which consists that tolerance not only is formed, but also develops in the course of interpersonal relations; and conditions created for its formation will help with tolerance development.

Being based on the researches spent by scientists, students should develop such skills by means of psychological trainings. Such psychological trainings are based on tolerance of the student - patience, understanding, effectively to react to any event, to make correct decisions in an extreme situation and to develop skills and abilities which are short-lived.

It is important to assert, that each teacher and student in higher education should form and develop in itself tolerance. Researchers have put in the forefront some skills and talents which are suitable to form tolerance in teachers and students, with following distinction:

- Ability to express tolerant sights and to defend position as personal opinion;
- Ability to be tolerant to opinion of others irrespective of, whether they differ from own opinion, that at others is own sights and that they have the right to express this opinion;
- Ability to be tolerant in conflict situations (inconsistent sights, conflicts of opinions).

For the present student it is easy to overcome difficulties which arise during his or her study, and even it will be easy to become an expert. Acquisition of this skill is a basis for achievement of success in higher education. When successful pupil succeeds, he gradually tests a spontaneous self-estimation and feeling of a self-estimation. We are convinced, that any graduate who has received the qualifying diploma, will bring the contribution to development of this branch and will serve in community sphere.

In summary, considering that fact, that tolerance is shown not only in interpersonal relations, but also among factors promoting success of educational activity, it is expedient to form such personal, human and psychological qualities in future teachers.

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